

February 28, 2022

Exploring Tomato Farmers Perceptions With A View to Produce Local F1 Hybrid Tomato Seeds in Buea, Cameroon

Author's Details:

Yannick Afanga Afanga^{1*} (yannickafanga@gmail.com), Eneke Esoeyang Tambe Bechem¹ (tamenekeso@yahoo.co.uk) and Egbe Enow Andrew² (egbe1@yahoo.com)

¹Department of Plant Science, University of Buea Cameroon.

²Faculty of Agriculture and Veterinary Medicine, University of Buea.

Corresponding author: Yannick Afanga Afanga, phone: +237674213723; email: yannickafanga@gmail.com

Received Date: 13-Jan-2022

Accepted Date: 18-Feb-2022

Published Date: 28-Feb-2022

Abstract

Tomato farming constitutes a major source of income for many youths in Buea and contributes to food security. Despite these benefits, tomato farming is not without challenges. This study was carried out to assess the challenges of tomato production and to investigate the agronomic strengths and weaknesses of tomato cultivars in Buea towards hybrid seed production. With the aid of semi-structured questionnaires and interviews, an exploratory survey was conducted to examine the perceptions of 153 tomato farmers on issues related to tomato farming. Results revealed the cultivation of 16 tomato cultivars in Buea. Cobra-F1 recorded the highest citation frequency (44.9%) of cultivation while Maruti-servo, Buea-tomato, Cherry tomato and Local-3 were least cited (0.4%). Majority of the farmers (98.8%) cultivated tomato from imported seeds while just 1.2% cultivated from seeds of the local cultivars. The production challenges include pests/diseases (38.8%), cost of chemicals (33.1%), cost of seeds (18.4%) and poor yield (9.7%). Farmers identified 9 disease-resistant cultivars and 6 cultivars with long shelf life of fresh fruits. Fungicide/pesticide application frequency (twice a week) exceeded manufacturers' prescriptions. This study has unveiled production challenges which will become breeding objectives. Moreover, this study will also serve as a pointer towards elite lines that may contain genes of agronomic importance. This study further gives baseline information that necessitate the collection and conservation of local tomato cultivars to prevent their extinction.

Key words: Tomato, Hybrid, Seed, Cameroon, Disease resistance, Fungicides, Insecticides, Cultivar.

INTRODUCTION

The current world population of 7.6 billion is expected to reach 8.6 billion in 2030, 9.8 billion in 2050 and 11.2 billion in 2100 (UN, 2017). The increase in world population will therefore require increased food production to guarantee food security. This required increase in crop production will need to occur in the context of mounting water scarcity, decreasing area and environmental degradation of arable land (partly caused by agriculture), increasing pollution, inevitable emergence of new races of pathogens and insect pests, and possible adverse effects of climate change. Thus, the task of increasing crop yields represents an unprecedented challenge for plant breeders and agricultural scientists. Biotic stresses remain the greatest constraint to crop production (Jain and Brar, 2010) accounting for 52% of the global yield loss (Suresh et al., 2013). Bacteria, viruses, fungi, nematodes, insect pests and weeds are considered to be biotic factors that limit crop production (Vincelli, 2018; Suresh et al., 2013; Godwin, 2007). For years, chemicals have been used to control biotic damage of crop plants. Nowadays, interest in the use of chemicals against biotic stress is decreasing because of its various limitations such as the requirement for more than one chemical application, an investment that is not affordable

February 28, 2022

by most small-scale farmers (Brading et al., 2002). Besides, using chemical spray may have adverse effects on human health and the environment, including beneficial organisms and may lead to the development of chemical-resistant pathogen races, insects, and weeds (Vincelli, 2018; Miedaner et al., 2013).

On the other hand, the use of resistant cultivars is currently seen as the best strategy, durable, economical, and environmentally friendly means of biotic stress control (Klarquist et al., 2016; Hansona et al., 2016; Ragimekula et al., 2013). Given the context of current yield trends, predicted population growth and pressure on the environment, traits relating to yield stability and sustainability is a major focus of plant breeding efforts. These traits include durable disease resistance, abiotic stress tolerance and nutrient and water-use efficiency (Slafer et al. 2005; Trethowan et al. 2005). Plant breeding will therefore play a key role in this coordinated effort for increased food production. Tomato is considered as one of the most widely grown vegetable in the world and the most extensively cultivated fruit vegetable in Cameroon (Tabe-Ojong et al., 2020), where it is grown in different parts of the country. Cameroon is among the major producers of tomatoes in the Central African sub-region with almost 1,068,495 metric tons in 2018 (FAOSTAT, 2018). Most of the tomato produced is consumed locally while just about 1% is exported to neighboring countries such as Equatorial Guinea, Nigeria, Tchad and Gabon (Tarla et al., 2015). Tomato consumption has gained importance due to its antioxidant property that reduces cancer incidences (Wamache, 2005). Moreover, lycopene, a major component of red tomatoes, has been shown to possess antioxidant properties and may help to protect against human diseases, such as cancer and heart diseases (Fajinmi and Fajinmi, 2010). Tomato is used as a fresh vegetable and can also be processed and canned as a paste, juice, sauce, powder or eaten whole. Tomato is an important dietary source of vitamins A and C.

Besides its role in ensuring food and health security, tomato farming constitutes a major source of livelihood for many youths in Buea who engage into it as a source of income. Regardless of all the many benefits of the crop, its production still faces myriad of challenges making it less profitable (Tabe-Ojong et al., 2020).

Some of these constraints can either be production, post-harvest, marketing or a combination of all of these (Tabe-Ojong *et al.*, 2020).

This study therefore aimed at investigating the production challenges and identifying the agronomic strengths and weaknesses of tomato cultivars in Buea towards local F1 hybrid seed production.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted in Buea sub division located on the eastern slope of Mount Cameroon between latitude 3°57' to 4°27'N and longitude 8°58' to 9°25'E with a mean annual rainfall of about 2800mm, received monthly between June and September (Egbe and Tabot, 2011). The mean annual temperature, relative humidity and sunshine are 28°C, 86% and 900 to 1200hrs per annum respectively (Egbe and Tabot, 2011). This study was carried out at five localities (Muea, Molyko, Great Soppo, Small Soppo and Bokwaongo) within the Buea municipality, Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon.

The research included a combination of interviews and use of semi-structured questionnaires with both open and closed ended questions. Data collection laid emphasis on tomato farmers' perceptions of tomato production issues such as tomato cultivars in Buea and their frequencies of cultivation, performance of various cultivars based on disease and pest resistance, shelf life of fresh fruits, available seed sources to farmers, challenges of tomato production, common tomato diseases, fungicide and insecticide application frequencies. The purposive simple random sampling technique was used to sample the views of 153 farmers on the named issues regarding tomato production. Descriptive statistics including frequency and percentages were used to summarize the data and results were presented in tables and figures.

RESULTS**i. Respondents' demographic information**

The demographic information of tomato farmers is presented in Table 1. It was observed that 77.1% of tomato farmers were males and 22.9% were females. Most of the respondents (39.2%) were within the age group "36-45" while the least (7.8%) represented were those above the age of 55. In terms of marital status, there were more single respondents (62.1%) than there were married respondents (37.9%). In view of longevity in tomato farming, 38.6% were in the range of "6-10" years while the least represented were those who have been farming tomatoes for more than 20 years (3.9%).

Table 1: Demographic information of tomato farmers in Buea

Parameter	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	118	77.1
	Female	35	22.9
Age group	25-35	57	37.3
	36-45	60	39.2
	46-55	24	15.7
	>55	12	7.8
Education level	FSLC	48	31.4
	O/L	47	30.7
	A/L	29	19.0
	First degree	23	15.0
	Master's degree	6	3.9
Marital status	Married	58	37.9
	Single	95	62.1
Longevity	1-5yrs	52	34.0
	6-10yrs	59	38.6
	11-15yrs	24	15.7
	16-20yrs	12	7.8
	>20yrs	6	3.9

ii. Tomato cultivars grown in Buea

Sixteen tomato cultivars were encountered in this study; of which 9 were hybrids while 7 were standard (open-pollinated) cultivars (Table 2). Of these 16 cultivars, 13 were imported while only 3 were local cultivars. Thus implying that 81% of the cultivated tomato seeds were imported. There was no local hybrid among these 16 cultivars. It is worth noting that 69% of the imported seeds came from a breeding company based in France (Technisem).

Table 2: List of tomato cultivars encountered in Buea

SN	Cultivar	Code	Type	Origin
1	Nadira F1	C1	Hybrid	France
2	American hybrid No. 7 F1	C4	Hybrid	USA
3	Cobra F1	C7	Hybrid	France
4	Lindo F1	C8	Hybrid	France
5	Lady Nema F1	C9	Hybrid	France
6	Maruti-Servo F1	C10	Hybrid	India
7	Barkker Brothers F1	C11	Hybrid	Holland
8	American hybrid NO. 5 F1	C12	Hybrid	USA
9	Rio Tinto F1	C13	Hybrid	France
10	Buffalo	C2	Standard	France

February 28, 2022

11	Rio Grande Plus	C3	Standard	France
12	Roma Savana	C5	Standard	France
13	Rio Grand	C6	Standard	France
14	Buea tomato	C14	Standard	Local
15	Cherry tomato	C15	Standard	Local
16	Local 3	C16	Standard	Local

iii. Cultivation frequencies of tomato cultivars cultivated in Buea

Out of the 16 tomato cultivars encountered in Buea, Cobra F1 recorded the highest frequency of citation (81.0%) while the least citation frequency (0.7%) was recorded by Maruti-servo, Buea tomato, Cherry tomato and Local 3 (Table 3). Results indicated that 84.8% of farmers cultivated hybrid cultivars while only 15.2% cultivated the standard (open-pollinated) cultivars. Moreover, 98.9% of farmers cultivated imported tomato seeds while just 1.1% of farmers cultivated seeds from the local cultivars.

Table 3: Cultivation frequencies of tomato cultivars encountered in Buea

SN	Cultivar	Type	Origin	Cultivation Frequency	Percentage cultivation frequency (%)	Cumulative frequency	Cumulative percent (%)
1	Cobra	Hybrid	Imported	124	81.0	124.0	44.9
2	Bakker brothers	Hybrid	Imported	42	27.5	166.0	60.1
3	Nadira	Hybrid	Imported	23	15.0	189.0	68.5
4	Lindo	Hybrid	Imported	12	7.8	201.0	72.8
5	Lady nema	Hybrid	Imported	12	7.8	213.0	77.2
6	Griffaton	Hybrid	Imported	10	6.5	223.0	80.8
7	AMH 5	Hybrid	Imported	6	3.9	229.0	83.0
8	AMH 7	Hybrid	Imported	4	2.6	233.0	84.4
9	Maruti-servo	Hybrid	Imported	1	0.7	234.0	84.8
10	Rio grand	Standard	Imported	12	7.8	246.0	89.1
11	Buffalo	Standard	Imported	6	3.9	252.0	91.3
12	Rio Grande plus	Standard	Imported	3	2.0	255.0	92.4
13	Roma savana	Standard	Imported	18	11.8	273.0	98.9
14	Buea tomato	Standard	Local	1	0.7	274.0	99.3
15	Cherry tomato	Standard	Local	1	0.7	275.0	99.6
16	Local 3	Standard	Local	1	0.7	276.0	100.0

iv. Seasonal variation of farmers' tomato cultivar preference in Buea

Cobra was the most cultivated tomato in both the dry season (26.8%) and the rainy season (58.2%) although its cultivation frequency in the rainy season exceeded that of the dry season by 31.4% (Table 4). On the other hand, Griffaton and AMH 7 were not cultivated during the dry season. Similarly, Rio grande plus and Rio grande were not cultivated during the rainy season.

Table 4: Seasonal variation of farmers' tomato cultivar preference in Buea

Cultivar	Dry season cultivars		Rainy season cultivars	
	Frequency	% freq.	Frequency	% freq.
Bakker brothers	18	11.8	18	11.8
Cobra	41	26.8	89	58.2
Nadira	12	7.8	12	7.8
Griffaton	0	0.0	10	6.5
Buffalo	2	1.3	1	0.7
Rio Grande plus	2	1.3	0	0.0
AMH 7	0	0.0	3	2.0
Roma savana	24	15.7	6	3.9

February 28, 2022

Rio grand	18	11.8	0	0.0
Lindo	2	1.3	8	5.2
Lady nema	6	3.9	12	7.8
AMH 5	1	0.7	2	1.3
Maruti-servo	1	0.7	1	0.7
Buea tomato	1	0.7	1	0.7
Cherry tomato	1	0.7	1	0.7
Local 3	1	0.7	1	0.7

v. Farmers’ sources of tomato seeds in Buea

It was noted that there were two sources of tomato seeds available to farmers in Buea viz: commercial shops and seeds saved from previous planting seasons. More than half (54%) of the tomato farmers’ population rely on commercial shops as their seed source, 16% depend on seeds saved from previous planting seasons while 30% of respondents rely on both sources (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Farmers’ sources of tomato seeds in Buea

vi. Common production challenges faced by tomato farmers in Bue

Common tomato production challenges in Buea include pests and diseases, cost of seeds, cost of chemicals and poor yields. Of these, the problem of pests and diseases is the most rampant as indicated by a frequency of 39% and next to this was the cost of chemicals (33%), while poor yield recorded the least frequency of citation (10%)(Figure 2).

February 28, 2022

Figure 2: Common production challenges faced by tomato farmers in Buea**vii. Common tomato diseases faced by tomato producers in Buea**

Among tomato diseases, three were commonly cited by tomato farmers (Figure 3) – late blight, tomato yellow leaf curl and bacterial wilt. Late blight was the most frequently cited (47%) of these and was followed by yellow leaf curl with a percentage frequency of 44% while bacterial wilt was the least common (43%).

Figure 3: Common tomato diseases faced by tomato producers in Buea**viii. Seasonal variation of fungicide and insecticide application frequency by tomato producers in Buea**

Based on findings, there was more application of fungicide in the rainy season than in the dry season while the reverse was true for insecticide application in their tomato fields in Buea (Table 5). It was found that 73.2% of farmers reported a “twice per week” fungicide application frequency in the rainy season as oppose to 26.8% respondents who reported an application frequency of once per week. On the contrary, in the dry season, 96.7% of the farmers apply fungicide once a week while a few (3.3%) applied it twice a week. For the insecticide application, 95.4% of farmers applied insecticide once a week in the rainy while a few (4.6%) applied it twice a week. In the dry season, 68.6% of the farmers applied insecticide twice a week while 31.4% applied it once a week (Table 5).

Table 5: Seasonal variation in fungicide and insecticide application frequency by tomato producers in Buea

Category of agrochemical	Application frequency	Rainy season		Dry season	
		Frequency	% freq.	Frequency	% freq.
Fungicide	Once per week	41	26.8	148	96.7
	Twice per week	112	73.2	5	3.3
Insecticide	Once per week	146	95.4	48	31.4
	Twice per week	7	4.6	105	68.6

ix. Respondents' opinion of disease-resistant tomato cultivars in Buea

Generally, respondents cited 9 tomato cultivars as disease-resistant cultivars (Table 6). Cobra was cited as the most resistant cultivar (100%) while Rio grande and AMH 7 were the least resistant as indicated by 7.8% of farmers.

Table 6: Respondents' opinion of disease-resistant tomato cultivars in Buea

SN	Cultivars	Frequency	% freq.
1	Cobra	153	100.0
2	Bakker brothers	89	58.2
3	Nadira	65	42.5
4	Roma savana	41	26.8
5	Buffalo	35	22.9
6	Lindo	30	19.6
7	Lady nema	18	11.8
8	AMH 7	12	7.8
9	Rio grande	12	7.8

x. Tomato cultivars with long shelf life of fresh fruits in Buea

Respondents identified 6 tomato cultivars whose fresh fruits have long shelf life. Cobra was the most cited among these 6 cultivars with a percentage frequency of 55% while Lady nema was the least cited with a percentage frequency of 3.5% (Table 7).

Table7: Tomato cultivars with long shelf life of fresh fruits in Buea

SN	Cultivar	Frequency	% freq.
1	Cobra	94	59.9
2	Bakker brothers	24	15.3
3	Nadira	23	14.6
4	Roma savana	12	7.6
5	Rio grand	12	7.6
6	Lady nema	6	3.8

DISCUSSION

The low level of education recorded for most respondents seem to have a negative impact on tomato production since it may have a direct effect on farm management practices as well as tomato marketing strategies. These findings were in conformity with Sethumadhava et al. (2016) who reported that the farmers' educational level has a major effect on the improvement of their total production and per capita income, since it impacts their farm management practices and control over diseases and insect pests. Sethumadhava et al. (2016) reported that almost all the farmers were illiterate in a pathological survey on disease incidence and severity of major diseases on tomato and chilli crops grown in Sub Zoba Hamelmalo, Eritrea. Based on this study, most farmers preferred hybrid cultivars but no local hybrid cultivar was encountered and because of this, all the farmers who cultivated hybrid cultivars were compelled to depend on imported seeds. This finding conforms with Tata et al. (2016) who stated that majority of vegetable seeds available in the market are imported by private distribution enterprises of which TROPICASEM is the biggest importer in Cameroon. Majority of the farmers buy their seeds from commercial shops while a few save seeds from previous seasons. Farmers' enormous dependence on hybrid seeds was hinged on their quest for high yielding disease-resistant cultivars. Hybrid seeds are known for their outstanding performance when it comes to yield and resistance to diseases. Heterosis is the engine behind this advantage of hybrid seeds over open-pollinated (standard) cultivars. Heterosis is the superior performance of heterozygous hybrid individuals compared with their homozygous parental inbred lines. The lack of local hybrids and high yielding disease-resistant open-pollinated cultivars continue to drive Cameroon's dependence

February 28, 2022

on imported seeds which constitute a major drawback on the country's economy as it leads to capital flight. Moreover, hybrid seed production is as much a labour-intensive process as it is a technical one and so seed importation doesn't only lead to capital outflow but equally creates employment in foreign countries while the major national challenge of unemployment in Cameroon remains. The bad situation is made worst by the fact that farmers have to keep buying these hybrid seeds every other planting season since F2 seeds saved from F1 hybrid parents don't perform as much as their F1 parents because of the inherent problem of segregating plant populations.

Common challenges of tomato production in Buea include pests and diseases, cost of seeds, cost of chemicals and poor yields. All these challenges may be attributed to the lack of local hybrid cultivars with efficient disease/pest-resistant attributes which might have reduced the cost of hybrid seeds in markets in Cameroon. As long as the problem of hybrid seed importation persists, the problem of high costs of hybrid seeds will remain. Moreover, the resistance offered by imported hybrid seeds to pests/diseases is often inefficient because of the problem of adaptability. This is so because these seeds were bred under environmental conditions that are different from ours and as such, they display performances that fall short of what is observed in the countries where they were bred. Furthermore, the durability of the disease/pest resistance offered by these hybrid cultivars comes under threat from the emergence of new strains of pathogens/pests over time. All these further aggravate the problem of pests and diseases and further augment dependence on chemicals and cost of production. It is worth noting here that these findings are in conformity with Tata *et al.* (2016) who equally reported high expenditure on chemicals by vegetable farmers in Cameroon.

Some common tomato diseases encountered by tomato farmers in Buea include late blight, tomato yellow leaf curl virus and bacterial wilt. These diseases have previously been reported in Cameroon by Kouam *et al.* (2018), Fontem (1993) and Fontem *et al.* (1999). Generally, it was found that fungicide application frequency is twice as much in the rainy season as it was in the dry season. The reverse is true for insecticide application frequency. This observation is probably owing to the fact that in the rainy season blight is more prevalent than in the dry season while insect pests are more prevalent in the dry season than in the rainy season. Blight is more prevalent in the rainy season because availability of moisture and rain droplets favour the spread of this disease while insect pests are more prevalent in the dry season because the conditions then are favourable for breeding. It is worth noting that these application frequencies violate manufactures' prescriptions for most of these fungicides and insecticides. Furthermore, for effective results, farmers often mix two or more of these fungicides and insecticides for a single application. By reason of implication, new strains of fungicide-resistant pathogens and insecticide-resistant pests may have evolved over time such that the spectrum of a single fungicide or insecticide may not be broad enough to achieve effective control. The excess application of fungicides and insecticides pose serious health risks to consumers and constitute a major threat to environmental sustainability. This over-dependence on fungicide and pesticide could be as a result of the synergistic effect of inadequate host plant resistance and the occurrence of a wide range of pests and pathogens following the conducive warm humid tropical climates. Nothing much can be done about the warm humid tropical climates but something can be done and needs be done urgently about improving the host-plant-resistance of the local cultivars. This study corroborates Suh *et al.* (2005) who equally reported the problem of over-application of fungicides by tomato farmers in Foubot (Cameroon).

CONCLUSION

Tomato production doesn't only combat food insecurity but also constitute a major source of livelihood for many youths in Buea who engage into it as a source of income. Tomato farmers in Buea almost entirely rely on imported seeds for cultivation and this comes with great economic implications like capital flight and creation of employment in foreign countries. The local tomato cultivars are at the verge of extinction because they are not preferred by farmers for economic reasons. Common challenges of tomato production in Buea include cost of hybrid seeds, pests and diseases, cost of chemicals and poor yields. Inadequate host-plant resistance and the

occurrence of a wide range of pest and diseases are fuelling over-application of fungicides and insecticides which itself poses health risks and threats to environmental sustainability. This study has unveiled production challenges which will become breeding objectives. Moreover, this study will also serve as a pointer towards elite lines that may contain genes of agronomic importance. This study further gives baseline information that necessitate the collection and conservation of local tomato cultivars to prevent their extinction.

REFERENCES

- i. Brading PA, Verstappen ECP, Kema GHJ, Brown JKM (2002) A gene-for-gene relationship between wheat and *Mycosphaerella graminicola*, the *Septoria tritici* blotch pathogen. *Phytopathol* **92**: 439-445.
- ii. Egbe, E.A., Tabot, P.T., (2011). Carbon sequestration in eight woody non-timber forest species and their economic potentials in Southwestern Cameroon. *Appl. Ecol. Environ. Res.* **9**(4), 369-385.
- iii. Fajinmi, A. A. and Fajinmi, O. B. (2010). An overview of bacterial wilt disease of tomato in Nigeria *Agricultural Journal*, **5**(4): 242-247.
- iv. FAOSTAT (2018). Retrieved from <http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/> on 3rd February 2019, at 5:59 pm.
- v. Fontem D.A. (1993). Survey of tomato diseases in Cameroon. *Tropicultura* **11**(3), 87-90.
- vi. Fontem D.A., Gumedzoe M.Y.D., Nono-Womim R.(1999). Biological constraints in tomato production in the western high lands of Cameroon. *Tropicultura*, 16-17, 2, 89-92.
- vii. Goodwin SB (2007) Back to basics and beyond: Increasing the level of resistance to *Septoria tritici* blotch in wheat. *Australas Plant Pathol* **36**: 532-538.
- viii. Hansona P, Lua SF, Wanga JF, Chena W, Kenyona L, et al. (2016) Conventional and molecular marker-assisted selection and pyramiding of genes for multiple disease resistance in tomato. *Sci Hort* **201**: 346-354.
- ix. Jain SM, Brar DS (2010). *Molecular techniques in crop improvement*. Springer Science+Business Media, Berlin, Germany.
- x. Klarquist E, Chen XM, Carter AH (2016) Novel QTL for stripe rust resistance on chromosomes 4A and 6B in soft white winter wheat cultivars. *Agronomy* **6**: 1-14.
- xi. Kouam E. B., Dongmo J. R., Djeugap J. F. (2018). Exploring morphological variation in tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*): A combined study of disease resistance, genetic divergence and association of characters. *Agricultura Tropica et Subtropica*, **51**(2), 71–82.
- xii. Miedaner T, Zhao Y, Gowda M, Longin CFH, Korzun V, et al. (2013) Genetic architecture of resistance to *Septoria tritici* blotch in European wheat. *BMC Genomics* **14**: 858.
- xiii. Ragimekula N, Varadarajula NN, Mallapuram SP, Gangimani G, Reddy RK, et al. (2013). Marker assisted selection in disease resistance breeding. *J Plant Breed Genet* **1**: 90-109.
- xiv. Sethumadhava R., Syed D., Sham K., Haben T., Rahwa T., Tomas H. (2016). Pathological survey on disease incidence and severity of major diseases on tomato and chilli crops grown in Sub Zoba Hamelmalo, Eritrea. *International Journal of Research Studies in Agricultural Sciences (IJRSAS)*, **2**(1) PP 20-31 ISSN 2454-6224.
- xv. Slafer, G. A., Araus, J. L., Royo, C. & Del Moral, L. F. G. (2005). Promising eco-physiological traits for genetic improvement of cereal yields in Mediterranean environments. *Ann. Appl. Biol.* **146**, 61–70. (doi:10.1111/j.1744-7348.2005.04048.x).
- xvi. Suh C., Mekontchou T., Mbouapouognigni V., Ngueguim M. and Njiayoum I. (2005). Tomato production in Foubot (Cameroon) in relation to dosage of fungicide application. *Journal of the Cameroon academy of sciences*, **5**(2).
- xvii. Suresh S, Malathi D (2013) Gene pyramiding for biotic stress tolerance in crop plants. *Weekly Sci Res J* **1**: 2321-7871.

February 28, 2022

- xviii. *Tabe-Ojong M.P. Jr., Molua E.L., Nzie J.R.M., Geogette L.F. (2020). Production and supply of tomato in Cameroon: Examination of the comparative effect of price and non-price factors. Scientific African 10 (2020) e00574.*
- xix. *Tarla D.N., Kamga A., Fontem D.A. (2015). Plight of pesticide applicators in cameroon: case of tomato (Lycopersicon esculentum mill.) farmers in foubot, J. Agricult. Environ. Sci. 4, 87–98.*
- xx. *Tata P.I, Afari-Sefa V., Ntsomboh-Ntsefong G., Ajebesone F.N., Nembangia J.O. and Billa S.F. (2016). Policy and Institutional Frameworks Impacting on Vegetable Seed Production and Distribution Systems in Cameroon, Journal of Crop Improvement, 30(2), 196-216.*
- xxi. *Trethowan, R. M., Reynolds, M., Sayre, K. & Ortiz Monasterio, I. (2005). Adapting wheat cultivars to resource conserving farming practices and human nutritional needs. Ann. Appl. Biol. 146, 405–413. (doi:10.1111/j.1744-7348.2005.040137.x)*
- xxii. *Vincelli P (2018) Genetic engineering and sustainable crop disease management: Opportunities for case-by-case decision-making. Sustain 8: 495.*
- xxiii. *Wamache A. (2005). Vegetable seeds handbook. Regina seeds Seminis. Printed by Bizone ltd. Nairobi Kenya.*